

TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC LITERACY OF STUDENTS BY MEANS OF THE METHOD OF THINKING

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ABSTRACT: this article covers the psychological aspects of the development of students' scientific literacy through the method of thinking. The article also outlines such points as increasing the scientific literacy of student youth using various techniques and supporting them in practice.

Keywords: student, thought, behavior, mental, factor, creativity, personality, moral, reasoning, idea, creativity, purpose, maturity, development.

ABSTRACT: Ushbu maqolada talabalarning ilmiy savodxonligini fikrlash metodi vositasida rivojlantirishning psixologik tomonlari yoritilgan. Shuningdek maqolada talaba yoshlarning ilmiy savodxonligi turli metodlar yordamida oshirish va amaliyotda qo'llab quvvatlash kabi fikrlar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: talaba, fikr, xulq, aqliy, omilkorlik, kreativlik, shaxs, ahloqiy, mulohaza, g'oya, ijodiylik, maqsad, kamolot, taraqqiyot.

Абстрактный : В данной статье освещаются психологические аспекты развития научной грамотности учащихся средствами метода мышления. В статье также изложены такие моменты, как повышение научной грамотности студенческой молодежи с помощью различных методов и поддержка на практике.

Ключевые слова: ученик, мысль, поведение, ментальность, факторность, креативность, личность, мораль, рассуждение, идея, творчество, цель, зрелость, прогресс.

In the realization of thinking in scientific literacy, the student arises such as thought, reflection, idea, hypothesis, purpose, and they are expressed in the consciousness of the individual as concepts, judgments, conclusions. Independent thinking manifests itself in close connection with language and speech, and they require each other in a continuous way. Therefore, the student, due to his independent thinking, speech, conscious behavior, is fundamentally different from being in existence. In the activity of independent thinking, the student determines the correctness, authenticity or their correspondence to reality and lack of understanding of what he reflects, perceives, perceives, imagines, remembers and phenomena. The perception of a person by a person, that is, the identification of the mental state of an unfamiliar person, its assumption, the collection of materials about the most necessary signs and signs,

is also a product of creative thinking. The process of cognition, consisting of this complex stage, requires from a person a volitional effort, mental seriousness, a conscious attitude, a stable situation, favorable conditions, through the direct influence of which a certain decision is made. The student's thinking activity is of a social nature. In the era of the social historical development of thinking, the need to first look for food for food, and then exchange interpersonal ideas, share experiences arose during the journey of making a working weapon and using them in their place. As a result of a person's introduction to mutual communication, treatment, attitude, expression of opinion, colloquial reading began to occur. Thanks to speech, the consistency, logic, systematicity of thinking products appeared, the possibility of leaving as a spiritual heritage for the future generation was born. When the systematized experiences, knowledge, skills and abilities accumulated by mankind were not left, human thinking could not achieve such tremendous success in the fields of Science, Technology, Culture. Thinking is a process similar to reading, writing, speaking and hearing. It is an active, coordinating process in which it covers thoughts about a fact in itself. Thinking is not a skill that is generated outside of context. Critical thinking is not even an educational program or a phenomenon that should be studied in conditions far from the general context of everyday life. Brown (1989) states that learning skills separated from task and real-life goals can give educators the opportunity to take objective tests well, but they cannot apply these skills in new situations. The definition of learning and thinking according to richer's interpretation is based on the results of research in the field of cognitive psychology, philosophy and education of the multimedia culture. Exchange of views. The process of thinking presupposes the mutual perception of the reader-youth. The fact that the reader-young people receive feedback lays the foundation for their commonality in learning from each other.

The reader-youth is required to reveal to others his abilities to a large thought and a simple mistake that they have as a thinker. When receiving a mutual opinion, the reader-youth is also required to restrain himself from listening carefully, forcing his system of views to the speaker and correcting other speakers. In response, the reader-youth will be able to use the gross opinions of others.

As a result of a wide range of discussions, the reader-youth will have a greater ability to analyze and identify the ideas they have, and will be able to push them into the system of ideas they have created in their knowledge and life

experiences. There are several models of its conduct in the organization of the thought process. They are:

- self-confidence;
- active participation in the work;
- exchange of ideas with comrades and teacher;
- being able to listen to the opinion of others.

The teaching system that ensures the multifaceted development of student students - that is, developing teaching-is understood as a system of teaching that focuses directly on the comprehensive development of the individual, the method, content, methods and forms of Organization of teaching. Today there are several theoretically based and practically significant teachings on developmental teaching. Also, in the proposed developmental teaching methodologies for the mental development of students, they are organized on the basis of a new principle of educational activity, satisfying the requirements of all pedagogical practices and successful in various educational institutions

As a result of the student's jumping of analytical thinking skills, the development of independent thinking is observed. The student's independent thinking may consist of the following stages:

1. The emergence of the problem in the field of student perception.
2. Understanding by the student the essence of the issue, problem, assignment.
3. The emergence of information or images similar to them.
4. Reduction of materials of imagination and memory, continuous birth of assumptions (hypotheses)
5. Step-by-step verification of assumptions or confirmation of their truthfulness.
6. The emergence and improvement of a new assumption.
7. Secondary verification of hypotheses (second confirmation).
8. Finding (solving) a problem, assignment, problem solution.
9. Continuation of involuntary mental behavior (relative duration of thoughts), etc. With its effectiveness, relevance, universality, independent thinking leads students towards professional training skills, lays a thorough foundation for understanding society and natural phenomena. From the research carried out, it can be seen that in methodological work aimed at the formation of thinking in the technological direction and the development of creative activity, which is one of the most important components of developmental teaching, individual elements of these components are scattered

in different directions, covering many types of students' activities. In this sense, they cannot adequately provide future technology teachers with the effective development of their creative activity and technological thinking in educational activities.

There are three main approaches to thought pedagogy:

1) the child's thinking develops by itself, the student receives knowledge at school, and the teacher helps him in this.

2) thinking must be specially developed until a special subject is created for the development of thinking.

3) thinking must be developed without interruption "production", that is, in the student's environment: at school and at home.

The technology for the development of student thinking is aimed at making independent decisions and choosing a direction in the study of the topic. thinking has 5 characteristics (D.Klester):

- First of all, this is independent thinking;
- Secondly, it is generalized thinking;
- Thirdly, this is problematic and evaluative thinking.
- Fourth, it is reasoned thinking;
- Fifth, it is social thinking.

This technology is based on a three-step lesson structure:

Stage I: difficulty (awakening existing knowledge)

Stage II: implementation (understanding)

Stage III: meditation

At the stage of difficulty, students are encouraged to further work, as well as to activate ("call") existing knowledge on a specific topic, which must first be clarified. A teacher can create a difficult situation by skillfully asking questions. By summarizing all of the above in this article, we can conclude that the technology for the development of critical thinking consists of creative methods that make the lesson interesting, strongly inform students about the study of the topic. The ability to work independently with information, that is, critical thinking, allows you to have a responsible attitude to the one who wants to learn all his life and his own education. The methods of developing critical thinking are not considered separately in this article, since the purpose of the article is somewhat different: in the means of (thinking, the student focuses on the thinking abilities of young people in general of the entire stratum of society, and then serves as the basis in scientific work. In conclusion, it should be noted that

the use of methods of tending, thinking and thinking information provides an opportunity to solve the following important tasks:

- reader-helps young people to realize their goals;
- provides activity in training; encourages effective discussion;
- helps the reader-young people themselves to compose questions and be able to ask it in the form of a question;
- reader-helps young people express their personal knowledge;
- supports student-youth personal reading motivation;
- creates a mood of respect for any thoughts;
- reader-helps young people grow their anguish for the characters

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